

GREEN ENERGY IN UKRAINE: POTENTIAL, ACHIEVEMENTS, AND FUTURE PROSPECTS

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Abstract

The current state of renewable energy development in Ukraine and its correlation with overall European energy trends has been examined. The key components of Ukraine's energy balance have been analyzed, including nuclear energy (49.2%), fossil fuels (28.5%), hydropower (11.8%), and renewable sources (9.8%). It has been identified that the share of renewable energy sources in Ukraine is significantly lower than the European average, where renewables account for 42% of electricity production.

The impact of military actions on the renewable energy sector has been considered, revealing substantial destruction of infrastructure, a decline in generation volumes, and a decrease in investment activity. It has been established that a significant portion of wind and solar power plants has been damaged or is located in temporarily occupied territories, leading to a reduction in total generation capacity and a slowdown in the development of new projects.

Key financial and regulatory challenges in the industry have been outlined, including tariff policy instability, debt obligations to renewable energy producers, limited access to investments, and the low efficiency of support mechanisms for green energy. It has been proven that without structural reforms in state regulation and the development of new financial instruments, further expansion of renewable energy remains at risk.

Possible ways to overcome the crisis and stimulate the development of renewable energy in Ukraine have been analyzed. The expansion of financing mechanisms, modernization of energy infrastructure, implementation of energy storage systems, and adaptation of the Ukrainian energy sector to European environmental standards have been proposed. The importance of developing decentralized generation and increasing the country's energy independence has been highlighted.

It has been concluded that the full-scale development of renewable energy requires comprehensive measures from the government, business, and international partners. Ukraine's active integration into the European energy market, implementation of decarbonization policies, and gradual transition to a sustainable energy system will contribute to strengthening the country's energy security and achieving an environmentally safe future.

Keywords: alternative energy, renewable energy, innovations, energy security, sustainable development, climate change, policy framework, technological advancements, European experience.

JEL classification: N70; O13; Q40

Problem Statement. Ukraine possesses significant potential in the field of renewable energy; however, its energy balance remains largely dependent on traditional sources such as nuclear power and fossil fuels. The share of nuclear energy in electricity production accounts for 49.2%, while coal and gas power plants contribute 28.5%. This indicates a low level of integration of green energy, necessitating strategic changes. Despite the substantial potential for the development of solar, wind, and bioenergy, their share in Ukraine's overall energy balance is only 9.8%. In comparison with Europe, where renewable sources account for 42% of electricity production, Ukraine lags significantly, highlighting the need for a comprehensive transformation of the energy sector [6-7].

The full-scale war has caused significant destruction of energy infrastructure, including renewable energy facilities. A portion of solar and wind power plants has either been occupied or suffered physical damage due to shelling, reducing the share of renewable energy generation by more than half compared to pre-war levels. The energy crisis and macroeconomic instability have significantly lowered the investment attractiveness of the green energy sector. Insufficient financing, limited access to credit, and payment instability pose additional risks for the development of new renewable energy projects in Ukraine.

The reduction of the feed-in tariff and irregular payments for generated electricity weaken incentives for the development of renewable sources. The lack of a clear regulatory policy and support mechanisms similar to European renewable energy incentive schemes complicates sectoral growth. The Ukrainian energy system's lack of flexibility, low transmission capacity, and the need for infrastructure modernization create obstacles to large-scale deployment of renewable energy. The absence of a developed energy storage market and balancing mechanisms further exacerbates these problems.

The European energy market is actively developing mechanisms for the export and import of renewable electricity. However, due to military actions and limited grid interconnectors, Ukraine faces significant challenges in exporting surplus green electricity, which hinders sectoral growth. The Ukrainian energy system remains centralized, making it vulnerable to attacks and increasing regional dependence on centralized generation. Implementing distributed generation mechanisms and developing local energy communities could enhance energy security.

The effective integration of renewable energy sources into the energy system requires advancements in energy storage technologies. In Ukraine, this sector is still in its early stages, creating difficulties in load

balancing. The lack of efficient energy storage mechanisms complicates the integration of renewables into the power system, as electricity generation from renewable sources is subject to seasonal and weather fluctuations. Government policy also plays a significant role in the development of green energy. Ukraine currently has legislative initiatives aimed at promoting renewable energy, but their implementation has been slow. Insufficient coordination between government agencies, energy companies, and investors creates additional barriers to the effective deployment of clean energy technologies.

Another challenge is the limited development of bioenergy, which has significant potential in Ukraine due to the large amount of agricultural waste. Despite this, the bioenergy sector remains underdeveloped due to the absence of incentive mechanisms and investments in relevant technologies. The growth of this sector could reduce dependence on imported gas and enhance the country's energy independence. Among other challenges, there is a lack of informational support and low public awareness regarding the benefits of renewable energy. The absence of active programs promoting green energy and environmental education slows down the adoption of new technologies and reduces public support for reforms in this sector.

Climate change and Ukraine's international environmental commitments necessitate more active development of renewable energy. Compliance with the Paris Agreement and adaptation to European standards require a gradual reduction of greenhouse gas emissions and a transition to a low-carbon economy, which calls for an accelerated expansion of renewable sources.

Given these challenges, Ukraine requires a comprehensive approach to developing green energy. Key priorities should include government support for investments, regulatory reforms, incentives for new technologies, and the implementation of effective energy system balancing mechanisms. Thus, the main obstacles to the development of green energy in Ukraine remain its dependence on traditional energy sources, the impact of military actions, insufficient investor support, the lack of effective renewable energy integration mechanisms, a weak regulatory framework, and low public awareness. Overcoming these challenges will enable Ukraine to transition to a more sustainable and environmentally friendly energy system, aligning with modern global trends and European requirements.

Analysis of Recent Research and Publications.

Ukraine possesses significant potential in the field of renewable energy, particularly in the development of solar, wind, hydro, and bioenergy. According to the European Environment Agency, the share of renewable energy in gross final energy consumption has been steadily increasing, driven by state support and international investments [7]. At the same time, the country's energy development strategy envisions a gradual transition to environmentally friendly energy sources and a reduction in dependence on fossil fuels [16]. However, the realization of Ukraine's green energy potential faces several challenges, particularly concerning the

functionality of the feed-in tariff mechanism, which affects investment attractiveness in this sector [11]. Despite these obstacles, the development of alternative energy sources remains one of the government's key priorities, as evidenced by the adoption of regulatory acts and international agreements such as the Kyoto Protocol [14].

In terms of international cooperation, Ukraine actively collaborates with the European Union and international organizations to implement European standards in the field of renewable energy [5]. Researchers note that the development of green energy can contribute to achieving the strategic goals of "Europe 2020," aimed at sustainable economic growth and energy security [2]. At the same time, scholars emphasize that full integration into the European energy system requires significant investments in the modernization of Ukraine's energy infrastructure [8].

In addition to economic challenges, the development of green energy in Ukraine requires solutions to technical issues, particularly the enhancement of energy storage and accumulation efficiency [10]. International studies indicate the promising nature of innovative bioenergy technologies, which could be utilized to improve energy efficiency in Ukraine [9]. Researchers also highlight the importance of maintaining energy balance, which would ensure the stability of electricity supply and enhance the competitiveness of Ukraine's energy system [12]. A major challenge remains the impact of military actions on the renewable energy sector. Analysis indicates severe infrastructure destruction, necessitating the development of new approaches to reconstruction and the expansion of energy capacities [22]. In this context, scholars stress the importance of international technical and financial assistance, which would facilitate the restoration of damaged facilities and the modernization of the energy system [23].

Despite these challenges, the development of renewable energy in Ukraine continues to be a priority for both state policy and international cooperation. The implementation of European standards, optimization of energy policy, and integration into global energy initiatives will contribute to the stable development of the sector. Experts emphasize that the further advancement of green energy requires improvements in legal regulation, increased investment, and the adoption of innovative technologies [3; 4; 6; 17].

Overall, Ukraine has all the necessary prerequisites for the effective development of green energy. However, the realization of this potential requires a comprehensive approach that includes state support, international cooperation, and the implementation of modern technologies [1; 18; 19; 20; 21; 24; 25; 26, 27]. Thus, the prospects for the development of green energy in Ukraine remain substantial, and with continued support from the government, international partners, and the scientific community, this sector can become a key element of economic recovery and the country's energy independence.

Formulation of Research Objectives. The aim of this study is to analyze the potential, achievements, and future prospects for the development of green energy in Ukraine in the context of global energy transitions and

sustainable development goals. The research focuses on assessing the impact of political decisions, economic incentives, and technological innovations on the growth of renewable energy sources in the country. Special attention will be given to challenges related to energy security, market integration, and the influence of geopolitical instability on sectoral expansion. The analysis of these aspects will facilitate the formulation of strategic approaches to enhance Ukraine's renewable energy potential and align it with European and global sustainability standards.

Main Content of the Study. Alternative energy in Ukraine is gaining increasing significance due to favorable natural conditions and the growing demand for sustainable electricity sources. High average wind speeds, significant solar radiation potential, and substantial agricultural waste volumes create conditions for the dynamic development of renewable energy sources (RES). This sector represents a critical strategic

direction in Ukraine's energy policy, contributing to energy independence and the decarbonization of the economy. The graphical materials presented in the figures illustrate the energy balance structure of Ukraine and Europe as of 2023. They depict the distribution of energy sources, enabling a comparative analysis between these two energy systems (Figures 1-2). In Ukraine, nuclear energy remains the primary source of electricity, accounting for 49.2% of total production. This dominance is attributed to the country's extensive network of nuclear power plants, ensuring stable electricity generation. In contrast, nuclear energy comprises only 25% of Europe's total electricity production [2].

Fossil fuels also play a crucial role in Ukraine's energy balance, with coal and gas power plants generating 28.5% of the country's electricity. This figure is comparable to Europe, where fossil fuels account for approximately 29% of total electricity production.

Energy Sources in Ukraine

Fig. 1. Sources of Energy in Ukraine

Source: Compiled based on [2, 6-8].

Renewable energy sources, including solar, wind, and biomass, contribute only 9.8% to Ukraine's electricity generation. This share is significantly lower than in Europe, where renewable sources provide 42% of the total energy balance. Hydropower in Ukraine constitutes 11.8% of the total electricity supply, making it an essential component of the energy system. In Europe, hydropower is included in the broader category of renewables, but it does not represent a dominant share of total energy generation. Other energy sources in Ukraine hold a minor share of only 0.6%, reflecting a

low level of energy resource diversification. In comparison, Europe's share of other energy sources reaches 4%, indicating a broader mix of energy solutions.

The analysis of these data suggests that Europe is significantly more oriented toward renewable energy, whereas Ukraine remains heavily dependent on nuclear power and fossil fuels. These disparities stem from differences in energy policies, investments in RES, and broader economic conditions.

Energy Sources in Europe

Fig. 2. Sources of Energy in Europe

Source: Compiled based on [2, 6-8].

The increasing share of renewables in Europe is a direct result of systematic government support and substantial investments in this sector. In Ukraine, however, the development of RES is hindered by the ongoing war, declining investment attractiveness, and the physical destruction of generation facilities. Nuclear energy remains the backbone of Ukraine's energy system due to its stability and high production capacity. Meanwhile, Europe is gradually transitioning toward more environmentally friendly energy sources, reducing reliance on conventional energy resources.

Fossil fuels, such as coal and natural gas, continue to be important for both regions. However, Europe is actively working to reduce their usage in favor of cleaner technologies. Despite aspirations to transform its energy sector, Ukraine is compelled to maintain a significant share of fossil fuels due to the instability of other generation sources. Hydropower holds a relatively larger share in Ukraine compared to other renewable sources. This is due to the country's substantial potential for hydroelectric power development, although its operation depends on hydrological conditions and requires modernization.

In the long term, Ukraine requires substantial investments in renewable energy to gradually reduce its dependence on nuclear and fossil-based generation. This shift aligns with the broader European decarbonization agenda. To achieve this goal, government support, electricity market reform, the creation of favorable conditions for investment, and post-war restoration

of damaged energy infrastructure are essential. Thus, the comparison of Ukraine's and Europe's energy structures highlights significant differences in development levels and approaches to electricity production. Given global trends, Ukraine has the potential for a gradual transition toward a more sustainable and environmentally friendly energy system.

Before the full-scale invasion, the share of renewable energy in Ukraine's total energy balance stood at 8.1%. In 2019, Ukraine was among the top ten countries with the fastest-growing renewable energy sectors and ranked sixth in terms of investment attractiveness in green energy. This progress was facilitated by the introduction of favorable governmental mechanisms, including the feed-in tariff and auction system for renewable energy development. By 2023, the share of renewable energy in total electricity generation, including large hydropower plants, increased to 22%, whereas in Europe, this indicator reached 42%. Despite the ongoing war, Ukraine continues to develop its renewable energy sector, as evidenced by the commissioning of 182.3 MW of wind power and approximately 500 MW of solar power in 2023 alone [6-7].

Solar energy remains the most dynamic segment of Ukraine's alternative energy sector. As of 2024, solar power plants accounted for approximately 75% of all renewable energy generation, excluding large hydropower plants. The country has favorable solar irradiation levels ranging from 1100 to 1500 kWh/m², making it highly suitable for the development of solar

energy infrastructure. However, over two years of war, approximately 13% of industrial solar power plants have been destroyed or severely damaged. The highest concentration of solar stations is found in the southern and central regions, while the eastern and northern regions have relatively lower levels of solar infrastructure. Despite these challenges, investments in solar energy continue, with approximately \$150 million invested in the sector in 2023.

Wind energy also demonstrates significant potential but has been severely impacted by military actions. Before the war, Ukraine operated 34 wind farms with a total of 699 wind turbines, generating electricity with an average capacity of 3.5 MW per turbine. However, a considerable portion of these wind farms is now located in temporarily occupied territories or has sustained damage due to hostilities. One of the most significant wind energy projects in 2023 was the Tyligul Wind Power Plant in the Mykolaiv region, with a capacity of 78 MW. This facility represents a key milestone in Ukraine's efforts to restore its wind energy sector and attract international investments.

Bioenergy remains an underdeveloped yet promising sector of Ukraine's alternative energy market. Given the country's vast agricultural sector, the potential for biomass production reaches 34 million tons per year, with primary raw materials including cereal straw, sunflower husks, and corn residues. Approximately 70% of bioenergy production relies on solid biomass, 15% on biogas, and another 15% on liquid biofuels. Utilizing agricultural waste for energy production contributes to reducing CO₂ emissions, enhancing energy independence, and creating jobs in rural areas. Hydropower has traditionally played a critical role in Ukraine's electricity generation, yet it has suffered substantial losses due to the war. Approximately 45% of Ukraine's hydropower capacity has been destroyed or severely damaged, with one of the most catastrophic losses being the destruction of the Kakhovka Hydroelectric Power Plant. The restoration of hydropower capacity remains an essential component of Ukraine's energy resilience strategy.

Nuclear energy continues to serve as the backbone of Ukraine's electricity sector. As of 2023, nuclear power accounted for 49.2% of total electricity generation, placing Ukraine sixth globally in terms of nuclear power production. While nuclear energy provides a stable source of electricity, diversifying Ukraine's energy mix by increasing the share of renewables remains a strategic goal.

Despite the war and economic difficulties, Ukraine possesses significant potential for renewable energy development. The restoration and expansion of renewable energy capacities are key priorities for achieving energy security and sustainable development. The country has all the necessary prerequisites to become a leader in renewable energy production. The implementation of strategic initiatives, the attraction of international investments, and the integration of innovative technologies will allow Ukraine to make a significant step toward a sustainable energy future.

The full-scale invasion by the Russian Federation has led to widespread destruction of Ukraine's energy

infrastructure, causing severe disruptions and instability within the energy system. The renewable energy sector has been among the hardest hit, with its share in total electricity production declining from 13.4% in 2021 to 5-6% in 2023 due to the destruction and occupation of energy facilities. The development of renewable energy remains a strategic priority for Ukraine's energy policy, aimed at increasing energy independence, reducing greenhouse gas emissions, and aligning with European decarbonization standards. However, the realization of Ukraine's renewable energy potential faces significant challenges, primarily due to the consequences of war, which have profoundly affected the infrastructure of renewable energy sources [8].

Before the invasion, the share of renewables in Ukraine's total energy balance was steadily growing, reaching 13.4% in 2021. However, by 2023, this figure had dropped sharply due to the destruction or capture of major energy facilities in temporarily occupied territories. As of 2022, Ukraine's installed renewable energy capacity stood at approximately 10 GW, with sector investments exceeding \$12 billion. However, with the onset of hostilities, a significant portion of energy infrastructure was damaged or destroyed. According to estimates by the Ministry of Energy, 75% of wind power stations and approximately 45-50% of solar power plants were taken offline. Large energy companies suffered the most significant losses, particularly DTEK, which lost three wind farms with a total capacity of 500 MW due to occupation. Similarly, Windkraft Ukraine lost access to five wind farms with a combined capacity of 335 MW. The loss of these facilities has severely impacted the functioning of Ukraine's energy system and has led to increased reliance on traditional energy sources.

In addition to physical destruction, the renewable energy sector has experienced financial instability due to accumulating debts and low market liquidity. Over the course of one year of war, the sector lost approximately 50% of its projected revenue, while the total level of debt exceeded UAH 18.2 billion. The primary reasons for this financial crisis include market restrictions, insufficient transmission tariff revenues, and inefficiencies within the state-owned enterprise "Guaranteed Buyer." These financial difficulties have complicated the attraction of new investments into the sector and have increased the risk of further reductions in the share of renewables within Ukraine's energy mix.

In response to the crisis, the Ukrainian Parliament has initiated the development of legislative mechanisms aimed at stimulating the growth of green energy. Key areas of reform include the introduction of renewable energy origin certificates to facilitate the integration of Ukrainian renewables into the European energy market, as well as the implementation of the Net Billing mechanism, which allows households to optimize the use of their own energy generation. Additionally, the legislation provides for the possibility of direct contracts between producers and consumers of electricity, which will enhance the competitiveness of the sector and increase its investment attractiveness.

Despite the challenges posed by the war, the restoration of the renewable energy sector remains a key

priority in the development of Ukraine's energy system. Expanding renewable energy generation is not only crucial for national energy security but also for economic stability and reducing the environmental impact of the energy sector. The adoption of new technologies in solar, wind, and bioenergy will enable Ukraine to align with EU standards and create a more efficient and environmentally friendly energy model.

Overall, the development of Ukraine's green energy sector depends on multiple factors, including the effectiveness of state policies, the attraction of international investments, and the modernization of energy infrastructure. Despite the current challenges, Ukraine has substantial potential to gradually increase the share of renewables in its energy balance, aligning with global trends in the transition to sustainable energy systems. The implementation of long-term strategic initiatives in this field will not only help mitigate the ongoing crisis in the energy sector but also lay the foundation for its sustainable development and integration into the European energy market.

Conclusions. The development of renewable energy in Ukraine is a key element in ensuring energy security, reducing dependence on fossil fuels, and aligning the energy system with European and global sustainable development standards. The country's natural potential, including favorable solar irradiation levels, high average wind speeds, and significant agricultural waste volumes, creates prerequisites for the dynamic expansion of the sector. However, realizing this potential requires systemic reforms, state support, and the attraction of international investments.

A comparative analysis of the energy balance structures of Ukraine and Europe highlights significant differences in approaches to electricity generation. While Europe heavily relies on renewable sources, their share in Ukraine remains relatively low. The primary reasons for this include a high dependence on nuclear energy, challenges in integrating renewable generation into the overall energy system, insufficient government support, and the consequences of military actions that have led to the destruction of many renewable energy facilities.

The war has posed a significant challenge to the development of renewable energy in Ukraine. Approximately 75% of wind power plants and a substantial portion of solar power plants have been damaged or are located in temporarily occupied territories. This has significantly reduced the share of renewables in the country's overall energy balance. Despite these challenges, investment activity in the sector continues, indicating the long-term viability of alternative energy.

Legislative initiatives aimed at stimulating the green transition could become a crucial factor in the sector's development. The introduction of green energy certification mechanisms, contracts for difference, and the Net Billing system will facilitate investment attraction and create a competitive environment in the energy market. At the same time, it is necessary to address issues related to financial compensation for renewable energy producers, improving conditions for electricity exports, and developing the local green energy market.

Nuclear energy remains the foundation of Ukraine's energy system due to its stability and high electricity production levels. Meanwhile, Europe is gradually reducing its reliance on nuclear power in favor of renewable energy sources. This underscores the need for a long-term strategy for integrating new technologies into traditional energy supply models in Ukraine.

Despite the challenges posed by the war, Ukraine has significant potential for the recovery and development of the renewable energy sector. Further expansion of renewable energy capacities, modernization of the existing energy infrastructure, and integration into the European energy system will contribute to enhancing the country's energy independence. Achieving this goal is possible through systematic state policies, effective investment attraction, and international technical support. Thus, Ukraine has all the prerequisites for a large-scale green transformation of its energy sector. The implementation of comprehensive measures aimed at supporting renewable energy can ensure the sustainable development of the energy system, reduce dependence on fossil fuels, and align with European climate and energy standards.

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